

An overview of agriculture extension in India

¹Rekha K

¹Research Scholar, Department of Studies in Economics, Vijayanagar Sri Krishnadevaraya University Ballari Karnataka, Karnataka, India

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13208705>

Corresponding Author: Rekha K

Abstract

Agricultural research and extension are critical for achieving food security and moving the rural poor out of poverty. Several studies have found that spending and investing in agricultural research and development (R&D), including extension services, is more beneficial than other forms of investment in decreasing poverty. This article will look at agricultural extension programs in India's public, private, and third sectors, focusing on their capacity to address farmers' information needs. India has one of the most extensive agricultural research systems in the world. Currently, the ICAR leads India's public research system, which includes 5 multidisciplinary national institutes, 45 central research institutes, 30 national research centers (NRCs), 4 bureaux, 10 project directorates, 80 all-India coordinated research projects (AICRPs)/networks, and 16 other projects/programs. There are also 29 state agricultural universities (SAUs) and one Central Agricultural University, which operate through 313 research stations. AICRPs serve as the primary link between the ICAR and the SAUs. The AICRPs encompass over 1,300 centers, with approximately 900 situated in agricultural universities and 200 in ICAR institutes. There are additionally Zonal Research Stations (ZRSs) and 200 sub-stations at the ICAR. Another ICAR organization that undertakes agricultural research and teaching is the National Academy of Agricultural Research Management (NAARM). As novel institutional models for the assessment, refining, and transmission of contemporary agricultural technologies, the ICAR has also built 8 Trainers' Training Centres (TTCs) and 611 Krishi Vigyan Kendras at the district level.

Keywords: Agriculture extension, Krishi Vigyan Kendras, state agricultural universities trainers' training centres, zonal research stations, etc.

Introduction

Extension agriculture approaches in India and throughout the world are evolving. Since the Green Revolution of both the 1970s and the 1980s, given the obvious inadequacy of the training and visit (T&V) program, Agricultural extension has adopted decentralized, participatory, and demand-driven approaches to increasing production through technology transfer (Birner *et al.* 2006; Birner and Anderson 2007; Davis 2008; Hall *et al.* 2000; Sulaiman and Hall 2008; Swanson 2014) [11, 1, 12, 13, 14, 10]. While there has been a push for a demand-driven agricultural extension for several decades, new methods of reaching out to farmers might have a huge influence in India since they may better represent farmers' local information requirements. Under India, agricultural extension is under transition. Following several years of neglect, public sector extension has received renewed interest and governmental attention in recent years. It is under pressure to change its mission as

well as its management, and it is also urged to collaborate closely with private and volunteer sector extension providers. Agriculture extension in India is under transition. Following long years of neglect, public sector expansion has recently attracted fresh interest and government attention. It is under pressure to reform its mission and administration, as well as to work closely with commercial and voluntary sector extension providers.

Review of Literature

Gershon Feder and Roger Slade (1986) [3] Comparative Analysis of Some Aspects of the Training and Visit System of Agricultural Extension in India The article compares the performance of the Training and Visit Extension system in one district of the Indian state of Haryana to the performance of an earlier extension system in a neighboring area. The statistics suggest a substantially greater level of village-level extension activity in the Training and Visit

Extension region, which is consistent with a large number of personnel and increased expenditure on the extension under this system. The results also indicate that knowledge of improved practices, particularly in wheat farming, spread more quickly in the region covered by T & V expansion.

Macro Ferroni and Yuan Zhou (2012) ^[5] Achievements and Challenges in Agricultural Extension in India This paper examines extension in terms of both primary production and market connections, and it recognizes the efforts of all extension providers, whether public or commercial. The goal of the extension is to provide guidance to farmers. Disparities in knowledge contribute to yield disparities. Services and high-quality inputs are critical productivity boosters. Their optimal application, however, necessitates understanding. Farmers also require knowledge of pricing and markets, post-harvest management, drivers of food quality, and safety norms. Some farmers amass their own expertise.

Hrideshwer Gupta and Dr. Sharda Shinde (2013) ^[6] Agricultural Extension in India This article will look at agricultural extension programmes in India's governmental, private, and third sectors. The paper examines the following topics: Extension Fundamentals, Importance of Agricultural Extension, Dimensions of Agricultural Extension, Farmer Information Needs and Preferred Information Medium, Agriculture Extension Approaches in India, Challenges to Traditional Extension Practises; Public and Private Extension, and General Extension Challenges and Constraints.

Rabindra Nath Padaria, P.C. Ranjit, Radhika Tanwar, and Simantini Shasani (2022) ^[6] State of Agricultural Extension reforms in India and need of convergence The current analysis discovered that the majority of the reforms were focused on a single subject, and even numerous reforms overlapped with identical mandates. This resulted in poor performance and limited accessibility to needy households. Furthermore, previous system modifications were refined during the epidemic. As a result, the study emphasizes the significance of convergence across common themes of numerous interventions implemented to improve extension services.

Objectives

1. To understand the agricultural extension system in India
2. Current situation of agricultural extension in India

Materilas and Methods

The study is based on secondary data gathered from various Articles, Websites, Papers, Wikipedia, Theses, Journals, Books, etc.

Results and Discussions

To understand the agricultural extension system in India

Execution of Agricultural Extension programs. The Extension Division, via its numerous programs, initiatives, and activities, assists farmers in obtaining information about scientific research and new knowledge in agricultural practices. It helps and encourages state governments to organize, manage, and run professional extension services. The Extension Division administers SMAE (Sub Mission on Agricultural Extension), a Krishonnati Yojana submission.

The Extension Division also manages the well-known ATMA Scheme, which assists state governments with their extension initiatives. The Division also assists farmers with their agricultural activities by providing information support. It collaborates with Prasar Bharati and All India Radio to ensure the smooth operation of the DD Kisan channel and Krishi Vani broadcasts. Kisan Call Centres have been set up at 21 sites across the country, encompassing all states and UTs, where farmers may call a toll-free number (1800-180-1551) and acquire information on their agricultural interests. The Extension Division also publishes four publications, two in Hindi and two in English, that give information on various elements of Extension operations and new innovations.

The Division also assists farmers with their agricultural activities by providing information support. It collaborates with Prasar Bharati and All India Radio to ensure the smooth operation of the DD Kisan channel and Krishi Vani broadcasts. Kisan Call Centres have been set up at 21 sites across the country, encompassing all states and UTs, where farmers may call a toll-free number (1800-180-1551) and acquire information on their agricultural interests. The Extension Division also publishes four publications, two in Hindi and two in English, that give information on various elements of Extension operations and new innovations.

Extension Division is also affiliated with an autonomous institute, the National Institute of Agricultural Extension Management (MANAGE). MANAGE's mandate is to establish connections between significant State, Regional, National, and international entities involved in Agricultural Extension Management. It also does agricultural extension research and training. More information regarding MANAGE may be found at www.manage.gov.in. The Extension Division operates four Extension Education Institutes (EEIs) in Nilokheri (Haryana), Hyderabad (Telangana), Anand (Gujarat), and Jorhat (Assam) to meet the training needs of field extension functionaries working in agriculture and allied departments of respective states/UTs

Extension Division Schemes the Agricultural Extension Sub Mission (SMAE) focuses on raising awareness and increasing the usage of relevant technology in agriculture and adjacent areas. It consists of four major components:

1. Assistance to State Extension Programmes in Support of Extension Reforms
2. Increased Assistance to Central Institutions
3. Agricultural Extension Media Support
4. Agriculture Graduates Establishing Agri-Clinics and Agri-Business Centres (ACABC).

Assistance to State Extension Programmes in Support of Extension Reforms

This plan, as the name implies, assists state governments with their Extension Activities. It intends to push extension system farmers through new institutional structures for technology distribution in the form of an Agricultural Technology Management Agency (ATMA) at the district level to operationalize extension reforms. Funds are distributed to state governments in accordance with the scheme's guidelines, which are also contingent on state governments releasing their part of the contribution.

Increased Assistance to Central Institutions

This initiative intends to increase the capacity of Extension officials as well as the skills of rural youth, farmers, and farm women. The Directorate of Extension (a subordinate office under the Extension Division), MANAGE, Hyderabad (an autonomous institute associated with the Extension Division), four Extension Education Institutes (EIs) at the Regional level, and the State Agricultural Management & Extension Training Institutes (SAMETIs) at the State level are among the prominent institutions involved in this effort.

The following are the scheme's key programs

A. Capacity-Building Programmes

- 1. Extension Education Institutes (EIs) The Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare has created four Extension Education Institutes in Haryana, Telangana, Gujarat, and Assam:** Nilokheri (Haryana), Hyderabad (Telangana), Anand (Gujarat), and Jorhat (Assam). These EIs meet the training requirements of middle-level field extension officials working in agricultural and related departments of respective states/UTs. EIs' programming activities include the organization of on-campus and off-campus training, workshops, and conferences in communication technology, extension methodology, training management, Agriculture Knowledge Information System (AKIS), and information technology.
- 2. MTCs (Model Training Courses):** The Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare has created four Extension Education Institutes in Haryana, Telangana, Gujarat, and Assam: Nilokheri (Haryana), Hyderabad (Telangana), Anand (Gujarat), and Jorhat (Assam). These EIs meet the training requirements of middle-level field extension officials working in agricultural and related departments of respective states/UTs. EIs' programming activities include the organisation of on-campus and off-campus training, workshops, and conferences in communication technology, extension methodology, training management, Agriculture Knowledge Information System (AKIS), and information technology.

B. Kisan Call Centre (KCC)

The project's goal is to answer farmers' questions over the phone in their native language. Currently, these call centers are located in 21 different states and territories. Kisan Call Centre has been assigned a national common eleven-digit Toll-Free Number 1800-180-1551. This number may be reached by mobile phones and landlines from any telecom network, including private service providers. Answers to farmers' questions are provided seven days a week from 6:00 a.m. to 10:00 p.m.

Farm Tele Advisors (FTAs) are Kisan Call Centre agents that have a bachelor's degree or higher in agriculture or connected fields and strong communication skills in their respective native languages. In phone conference mode, questions that cannot be handled by FTAs are sent to higher-level specialists. These professionals are subject matter experts from state agricultural departments, ICAR, and state agricultural universities.

C. Skill Development Programmes

- 1. Rural Youth Skill Training (STRY):** The component's goal is to train rural adolescents, rural craftsmen (blacksmiths, carpenters, etc. who design/manufacture agricultural equipment), and farm women throughout the country. This component's training focuses on specific occupational areas in agriculture and associated sectors. Both public and private/non-governmental institutions, including vocational training groups and youth organizations (such as Nehru Yuva Kendra), are actively participating in the program's execution.
- 2. DAESI (Diploma in Agricultural Extension Services for Input Dealers):** Agri-Input Dealers in the country is a valuable source of agricultural knowledge for the farming community, in addition to providing inputs and finance. However, the vast majority of these sellers lack proper agricultural education. A self-financed "One-year Diploma in Agricultural Extension Services for Input Dealers (DAESI) Programme" was launched in 2003 with a course fee of Rs.20000/- to the input dealers in order to build their technical competency in agriculture and to enable them to better serve the farmers and act as Para-Extension professionals. The National Institute of Agricultural Extension Management (MANAGE) is the program's nodal agency.

Agriculture Graduates Establishing Agri-Clinics and Agri-Business Centres (ACABC)

This curriculum attempts to tap into the skills of the enormous pool of Agriculture Graduates. They might open their own Agri-Clinic or Agri-Business Centre and provide farmers with professional extension services. Agribusiness Centres would give free/paid services/advice to farmers in order to increase agricultural productivity and income. This is important in two ways: it provides jobless agricultural graduates with chances for profitable self-employment and it enhances public extension efforts by offering consulting and extension services, including know-how, to farmers at the grassroots level.

Overview of agricultural extension in India

India boasts one of the world's most extensive agricultural research systems. The ICAR currently leads India's public research system, which includes 5 multidisciplinary national institutes, 45 central research institutes, 30 national research centers (NRCs), 4 bureaux, 10 project directorates, 80 all-India coordinated research projects (AICRPs)/networks, and 16 other projects/programs. There are also 29 state agricultural universities (SAUs) and one Central Agricultural University, which operate through 313 research stations.

AICRPs serve as the primary interface between the ICAR and the SAUs. The AICRPs encompass over 1,300 centers, with approximately 900 situated in agricultural universities and 200 in ICAR institutes. There are additionally Zonal Research Stations (ZRSs) and 200 sub-stations at the ICAR. The National Academy of Agricultural Research Management (NAARM) is another ICAR organization that conducts agricultural research and training. As novel institutional models for the assessment, refining, and

transmission of contemporary agricultural technologies, the ICAR has also built 8 Trainers' Training Centres (TTCs) and 611 Krishi Vigyan Kendras at the district level.

Agriculture Extension Services Provided by the Government

The extension system, combined with pricing policy and procurement support, is widely recognized for ushering in India's Green Revolution in the 1960s. However, by the end of the 1970s, the Indian public agricultural extension system had begun to deteriorate. By this point, the system was primarily involved in the delivery of agricultural inputs via state agriculture depots, as well as the administration of subsidies granted through various agricultural development programs. As a result, the system was criticized for becoming a monolithic organization with no clear purpose (Babu et al. 2013) [16].

1. The Training and Visiting (T&V) program of the World Bank
2. Agriculture Technology Management Agency (ATMA)
3. NMAET stands for National Mission on Agriculture Extension and Technology.
 - NMAET is made up of four submissions:
 - Agricultural Extension Sub-Mission (SMAE)
 - Seed and Planting Material Sub-Mission (SMSP)
 - Agricultural Mechanisation Submission (SMAM)
 - Plant Protection and Plant Quarantine Submission (SMPP)

Findings

1. Farmers and agricultural communities in India have developed a big bank of coping strategies and inventive practices through centuries due to the vast range of farming situations. These are restricted to informal channels within a specific geographical area and seldom move beyond a district, much alone the State. To capture the vast data banks of local knowledge accessible in different sections of the country, innovation networks allowing an open two-way flow of ideas and technology must be created and deployed. Digital technology will play a significant role in attaining this aim in a cost-effective manner.
2. Agriculture extension services in India are mostly focused on crop husbandry, with a strong emphasis on technology transfer (ToT). Crop husbandry received around 70% of the agricultural R&E budget, while agriculture extension received 92% of the crop husbandry budget. The objective of public sector extension is to provide all farmers with a one-size-fits-all product. This is a self-limiting strategy in a country where over 86% of farmers are classified as small and marginal because huge variations in resource endowment, agro-climatic conditions, and legal exigencies are not factored into the model of agriculture extension being followed by either the government or the private sector.

Conclusion

The government must adapt by closing the numerous remaining gaps in collaboration with private for-profit and non-profit entities. This could open the way for commercial Agri service delivery to underserved areas of the country in

the future. Every crop and state should be scrutinized by the government. Funding may emerge as a limitation, but other hurdles, such as political commitment to agriculture, institutional and implementation challenges, management, and organization, are likely to loom bigger. Implementation challenges are frequently highlighted as a barrier in Indian agricultural and rural development, raising the question of how the government might infuse skills, motivation, a sense of mission, and regeneration where they are required. During its pilot phase, ATMA looked to have put together the ideal circumstances. According to the 2010 Guidelines, it must now integrate job conceptualization from above with the necessary resources, advice, and empowerment from below. ATMA organizations at the block level play an important role. Farmers' representatives and local structures should develop recommendations for district approval. Making this procedure function is of the utmost importance.

References

1. Anderson JR, Feder G. Agricultural extension. In: Handbook of Agricultural Economics. Elsevier. 2007;3:2343-2378. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1574-0072\(06\)03044-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1574-0072(06)03044-1)
2. Saravanan R, Bhattacharjee S. Mobile phone applications for agricultural extension in India. Mobile phones for agricultural extension: Worldwide mAgri Innovations and Promise for Future. (Edited by Saravanan, R); c2014. p. 1-75.
3. Feder G, Slade R. A comparative analysis of some aspects of the training and visit system of agricultural extension in India. Journal of Development Studies. 1986;22(2):407-428. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220388608421987>
4. Ferroni M, Zhou Y. Review of agricultural extension in India. Syngenta Foundation for Sustainable Agriculture; c2011. p. 1-49.
5. Ferroni M, Zhou Y. Achievements and challenges in agricultural extension in India. Global Journal of Emerging Market Economies. 2012;4(3):319-346. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0974910112460435>
6. Gupta H, Shinde S. Agricultural extension in India. International Journal of Management and Social Sciences Research. 2013;2(11):25-38.
7. Kumar M. Agriculture: status, challenges, policies and strategies for India. International Journal of Engineering Research. 2019;8(12):1-5.
8. Rasheed SV. Agricultural extension in India: current status and ways forward. Background Paper for the Roundtable Consultation on Agricultural Extension, Beijing; c2012. p. 01-34.
9. Singh AK, Burman RR. Agricultural extension reforms and institutional innovations for inclusive outreach in India. In: Agricultural Extension Reforms in South Asia. Elsevier; c2019. p. 289-315. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-818752-4.00016-3>
10. Singh KM, Meena MS, Swanson BE, Reddy MN, Bahal R. In-Depth Study of the Pluralistic Agricultural Extension System in India; 2014. p. 01-166.
11. Birner BJ. Semantic and pragmatic contributions to information status. Acta Linguistica Hafniensia. 2006;38(1):14-32.

12. Davis N. Global interdisciplinary research into the diffusion of information technology innovations in education. *Researching IT in education*. 2010;21:158-66.
13. Hall BL, Denton GH. Radiocarbon chronology of Ross Sea drift, eastern Taylor Valley, Antarctica: Evidence for a grounded ice sheet in the Ross Sea at the last glacial maximum. *Geografiska Annaler: Series A, Physical Geography*. 2000;82(2-3):305-336.
14. Hall A, Sulaiman RV, Bezkorowajnyj P. Re-framing technical change: livestock fodder scarcity revisited as innovation capacity scarcity: Part 2. A framework for analysis; 2008. p. 01-26.
15. Padaria RN, Ranjith PC, Tanwar R, Shasani S. State of Agricultural Extension reforms in India and the need of convergence. *Current Science* (00113891). 2022;123(3):1-264.
16. Hirel J, Gaussier P, Quoy M, Banquet JP, Save E, Poucet B. The hippocampo-cortical loop: spatio-temporal learning and goal-oriented planning in navigation. *Neural Networks*. 2013;43:8-21.

Creative Commons (CC) License

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) license. This license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.